

available for all teachers, students, doctoral fellows and residents. However, the developing Semantic web services need continuous evaluation and monitoring, since drawbacks arise in data retrieval and result errors because of information import from external datasets. To overcome the limitations of intelligent processing, we should focus in the accuracy and expressiveness of an integrated biomedical education ontology.

Keywords: semantic web, ontologies, linked data, e-learning

Open Research Data in Biomedicine: A Step Forward in Defining an Italian National Policy

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Abstract: Open science paradigm is gaining increasing impact among stakeholders of scientific communication system by fostering visibility, free access and sharing of research results (publications and data) in the biomedical field.

In this framework, the concept of re-affirming openness to research output has been strengthened by the current EU funding research programme Horizon 2020. According to recent EC Guidelines, data generated by H2020 projects through the Open Research Data Pilot have to be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, thus reflecting the approach that publicly-funded scientific information should be available online.

In early 2017 the BISA (Bibliosan for Open Science) inter-institutional Working Group, including scientific information experts mainly from Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS, Italian National Institute of Health) carried out a survey on the practical handling of research data produced by Bibliosan affiliated institutions, the Italian Biomedical Research Libraries Network promoted by the Italian Ministry of Health. The BISA online questionnaire collected over 2,400 responses obtained from 58 Bibliosan institutions. Among the various aspects of data management covered by the BISA Questionnaire - data types and format, data archiving, ethical and legal aspects, accessibility and re-use, infrastructures and services –that one referring to the need of a policy and guidelines for dealing with research data was deeply investigated.

As a further action in view of defining a policy to be adopted by Bibliosan research institutions, BISA Working Group, coordinated by BISA ISS members, is currently circulating, for internal feedback, a draft roadmap concerning research data definition and typology, management, sharing modalities, roles and responsibilities of data producers and administrators, data protection and technical aspects relating to infrastructures and services. The main goal is firstly raising awareness in ISS research community, in order to gather comments and different views on this delicate matter.

Once carried out this preliminary round reflecting ISS perspective on the management of research data and according to the Italian Ministry of Health guidelines, the policy will be circulated among Bibliosan institutions to receive further feedback from a large number of bodies involved in biomedical research as well as in health care.

Along this agenda of initiatives, the BISA Working Group is keeping close contacts with a similar Study Group operating within the Conference of Italian University Vice-Chancellors (CRUI, Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane) the main Academic Authority grouping all Italian universities.

Keywords: biomedical research, open data, information dissemination, access information, Italy

Openness in Evaluation: Understanding Epistemological Challenges, Rethinking Competencies and Library Practices

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Abstract: Over the last two decades, “open” has become a buzzword nurtured by diverse “open” movements – Free and Open Source Software, Open Access, Open Science, Open Data, Open Government and others. Avoiding the discussion about the definition(s) of what seems to be a polarized and highly contextual term (Neylon, 2017), we will consider here that the concept of “open” refers to an environment that facilitates opportunities to participate in information and knowledge production and circulation for people who have been historically excluded. Policy making, programmes, initiatives and projects associated with these open movements

Evaluation is (or, at least, should be) a vital part of every effective policy, programme, initiative or project framed by these open movements. Sound evaluation strategies, procedures and criteria are needed to assess the impact of open movements on science, society and policy. Fostering access, collaboration and participation of groups that are in traditionally “peripheral” positions with respect to decision-making also means including them in evaluation processes, namely by employing participatory methods.

Using a meta-evaluative and transdisciplinary approach, this paper aims to discuss how Research on Evaluation developed within Information Science can contribute to enhance stakeholders and citizens’ involvement in Open Science through evaluation.

The discussion of the tendency to openness is structured around the interconnections between participatory methods and evaluation, highlighting the epistemological challenges in Information Science.

The transdisciplinary concept of co-evaluation is presented, as well as its emerging role in Open Science and Information Science.

Based on the results of a line of research that intersects Library and Information Services performance evaluation with sustainability transitions management and competences development carried out, since 2012, at the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities of the Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, two outputs that can significantly contribute to improve stakeholders’ participation in Open Science are examined: (1) the methods and procedures for assessing the impacts of libraries proposed in ISO 16394 (2014), enriched by the application of the criteria used in the Action Catalogue of Engage2020 for determining the level of stakeholder/public involvement in research and innovation; and (2) the domains and competencies of a (co-)evaluation framework, built on the contributions of taxonomies of evaluator competences elaborated by several authors and organizations (King et al., 2001, among others).

We conclude this paper by providing a research agenda for “open evaluation” discussion within Library and Information Services’ practices, where the involvement